

PLANETARY Health Cluster

FORMED BY

SPRINGS

Joint Scientific Strategy of the Planetary Health Cluster

Deliverable no. 7.17 (GoGreen Next), D4.16
(PLANET4HEALTH), 6.11 (MOSAIC), D1.5 (SPRINGS), and
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Author(s)	Tadhg MacIntyre (GoGreen Next), Suzana Blesic (PLANET4HEALTH), Emmanuel Roux (MOSAIC), Vanessa Harris (SPRINGS), and Marina Treskova and Uliana Kachnova (TULIP)
Co-author(s)	
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1. Introduction

This document outlines the scientific strategy and synergy-enhancing activities within the **Planetary Health Cluster**. The Cluster started its activities on **January 1, 2024**. The Cluster was kicked off at the meeting in Brussels in June 2024, under the auspices of the final conference of the Horizon 2020 project GoGreen Routes, in Brussels. The Cluster consists of the five projects funded under the **Horizon Europe topic HORIZON-HLTH-2023-ENVHLTH-02-01: GoGreenNext, MOSAIC, PLANET4HEALTH, SPRINGS, and TULIP**. These projects aim to improve the identification, monitoring, and quantification of the direct and indirect impacts of environmental changes and degradation on **Planetary Health**.

The Planetary Health Cluster was established by the European Commission to enable the five projects to:

- **Harmonize approaches** across projects;
- **Promote synergies and networking** among consortiums;
- **Avoid overlaps and redundancies** in research and activities;
- **Strengthen the Science4Policy link** to inform decision-making;
- **Streamline information flows** between projects and stakeholders;
- **Improve communication and dissemination** of results; and
- **Increase the overall impact** of the research.

The Cluster's overarching objective is to **clarify the costs and benefits of action and inaction** in mitigating and adapting to environmental changes. The main objectives of the Planetary Health Cluster are to:

1. **Promote and disseminate environment and health research** from a Planetary Health perspective;
2. **Raise awareness** of the health impacts of environmental changes and the costs and benefits of mitigation and adaptation interventions;
3. **Maximize the communication and dissemination** of results through the projects' networks;
4. **Contribute to evidence-based decision-making** and stronger EU and global policies; and
5. **Build capacity** around environment and health research.

2. Overview of the Projects in the Planetary Health Cluster

The five projects within the Cluster address various aspects of Planetary Health, focusing on the intersection of environmental degradation and human, animal, and ecosystem health. Below is a summary of each project's main objectives and focus areas:

GoGreen Next:

- **Main Objective:** Addressing a range of solutions to climate challenges across diverse contexts that promote human and environmental health.
- **Focus Areas:** Physical activity, sedentary behaviour, mental health, climate cognitions, COPD/asthma, air and noise pollution, and biodiversity access in urban environments.
- **Methodologies:** Virtual reality tools, digital dashboards, participatory approaches and health impact assessment.

TULIP:

- **Main Objective:** Investigating interactions between climate change, antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and plastic pollution in aquatic environments.
- **Focus Areas:** Climate change, biodiversity, freshwater change, and system-level problems of AMR-plastic interactions.
- **Methodologies:** Multi-method approaches, including environmental science, social science, and modeling (e.g., spatio-temporal, machine learning, and scenario-based models).

SPRINGS:

- **Main Objective:** Studying the intersection of climate change, water quality and quantity, and pathogen-specific diarrheal diseases to inform evidence-based policy
- **Focus Areas:** Climate change, water scarcity, river basin and urban flooding, microbial water quality, childhood health and diarrheal diseases.
- **Methodologies:** Downscaled climate projections, environmental sciences, modelling (hydrologic, microbial, agent-based, epidemiologic), prospective microbial water quality and diarrheal surveillance, economic and social sciences, and policy translation.

PLANET4HEALTH:

- **Main Objective:** Addressing vector-borne diseases, air pollution, PFAS contamination, and mental well-being.

- **Focus Areas:** Climate change, pollution (air quality, PFAS contamination), biodiversity, and mental health in environmental degradation contexts.
- **Methodologies:** Climate and environmental sciences, technology platforms, economic and social sciences, and policy translation.

MOSAIC:

- **Main Objective:** Developing and implementing information ecosystems for stakeholder engagement and open science.
- **Focus Areas:** Extreme climatic events, land use change, and their impacts on health and well-being local border communities, in East Africa and the Amazon region.
- **Methodologies:** Open Science, including engagement of all stakeholders in production of data and knowledge (participatory approaches), FAIR principles, open data infrastructures, and open dialogue between knowledge systems.

3. Scientific Synergies

The scientific strategy of the Planetary Health Cluster is structured around several **key components**, which are addressed by projects in varying degrees:

3.1. Problem Complexity within the Planetary Health boundaries

All projects address **single or multiple issues** related to climate change, including extreme climate events, biodiversity loss, and pollution. Four projects (SPRINGS, TULIP, PLANET4HEALTH, and MOSAIC) additionally overlap in their work on freshwater change, which they tackle from research of the changes of aquatic environment, through examining various sources of water contamination (microbial pathogens, plastics, PFAS, or mining as one of the causes of land use changes and connected water contamination), to focusing on issues of waterborne disease including diarrheal disease and AMR.

3.2. Methodology Complexity

All projects employ **multi-method and mixed-method approaches**, combining climate and environmental sciences approaches with those of social sciences, data analysis and modelling, and use of co-creation or participatory approaches.

Of all the methodological approaches to issues of interest to individual projects, the **utilization of social sciences** is the one area that is common to all projects in the Cluster and is thus

the primary point of focus for synergetic work. For example, MOSAIC realization will be defined through participatory approaches and community engagement; TULIP will utilize qualitative Human Centered Design research to develop community-tailored interventions, Integrated Knowledge Translation to bring scientific knowledge to stakeholders and engage them in the research, as well as citizen science for alerting to plastic pollution, clean beaches together, water testing with students, and raising awareness; and GoGreen Next will investigate perception of climate change risks and hope, perception of nature-based solutions. GoGreen Next will also address pathways for mitigation through behavior change which is similar to PLANET4HEALTH's interest in behavioral changes that are leading to policy changes; PLANET4HEALTH will work on vulnerability assessments by way of use of social sciences; while SPRINGS will use participatory research to discern local community understanding and existing adaptation to climate risks of diarrheal diseases, surveys of local, regional, national and international stakeholders, and study of how academic research is translated and understood by policy makers.

Interdisciplinary integration is another key focus of several projects, with projects like MOSAIC, SPRINGS, GoGreen Next, and PLANET4HEALTH emphasizing stakeholder engagement and transdisciplinary research.

3.3. Human, Animal, and Environmental Health Issues

System-level thinking is employed by all the projects, particularly in projects like TULIP and SPRINGS, which use a Planetary Health perspective to integrate human, animal, and ecosystem health.

Human health issues addressed by the projects in the cluster include physical activity and mental wellbeing (e.g. GoGreen Next), respiratory diseases, vector-borne diseases, exposure to plastics and plastic-associated antimicrobial resistance (TULIP), and diarrheal deaths and malnutrition in under-5 children (SPRINGS).

Animal health issues include antimicrobial resistance (TULIP), the impact of environmental changes on wildlife, livestock, and pets (as in PLANET4HEALTH), and zoonoses such as *Cryptosporidium*, *Giardia*, and *Campylobacter* (SPRINGS).

Environmental health issues focus on pollution (air, water, soil), biodiversity loss, extreme climatic events, land use changes, food-borne transmission as connector animal and human health, and the spread of bacterial, viral, and parasitic pathogens, AMR, and plastics in aquatic environments.

3.4. Data and Models

Projects will generate **data** on water quality, microbial contamination, air pollution, mental well-being, perceived state of health by communities, animal distribution and health and land

cover/land use. In addition, projects will utilize various forms of climate, environmental, and animal and human health historical data (such as epidemiological and socioeconomic records). Details about the data are outlined in the Cluster Data Management Plan.

Models developed within the Cluster include spatio-temporal regressions, hydrological models, machine learning models, and agent-based models for scenario analysis and risk assessment. Some of the projects (GoGreen Next, SPRINGS, and PLANET4HEALTH) will work with climate modelling. These models will produce downscaled climate data and climate projections, and bioclimatic datasets.

All the collected datasets will be **catalogued** by the Working Group 2 of the Cluster and will potentially be available for use within the Cluster. The management of these datasets will be explained in detail in the Cluster's Data Management Plan.

3.5. Open Science and Policy Relevance

The whole Cluster is committed to **open science**. As part of that commitment, the projects will address open access to resources and outcomes, to data, tools, and publications. Projects MOSAIC and TULIP consider open science in its broader sense (as, for example, per UNESCO recommendations¹), including co-creation and participatory activities, to equip implementation of interventions for One Health. This will help define embedded mitigation and adaptation actions.

Open science will be **one of the main focuses** of the continuing Cluster dialogue for joint actions, to help develop efficient co-production of knowledge, knowledge integration into actionable knowledge graphs, systems and models, and to foster development of recommendations and new Planetary Health policies.

Policy-relevant science is a key focus, with projects engaging policy makers through workshops, health technology assessments (HTA), and policy translation.

3.6. Vulnerability and Equity

All projects address **vulnerability and equity** by identifying at-risk populations (e.g., children, the elderly, migrants, indigenous communities, or other affected local communities) and incorporating participatory approaches to ensure equitable access to data, knowledge, and priority setting.

¹ <https://3.130.221.114/2021/12/02/unesco-recommendation-on-open-science-ratified/>

3.7. Tools and Risk Assessments

All projects will develop **tools** for risk assessment, early warning systems, and data dissemination, tailored to the needs of end-users such as policymakers, One Health professionals, and local communities.

3.8. Nature-Based Solutions

Projects TULIP, GoGreen Next and SPRINGS, each explore **nature-based solutions** such as artificial wetlands for water treatment, reforestation to mitigate environmental degradation or urban parks to mitigate noise and air pollution.

4. Opportunities for Collaboration

4.1. Water Contamination and Aquatic Environments

TULIP, **SPRINGS**, and **PLANET4HEALTH** all address water contamination, albeit from different angles (AMR, plastics, microbial pathogen contamination, and PFAS contamination). There is an opportunity to **share data and harmonize models** related to water quality, hydrologic modelling, and contamination sources and consider co-benefits when assessing interventions.

Collaboration Opportunity: Joint workshops or working groups focused on water contamination, where projects can share methodologies, data, and tools for monitoring and mitigating water pollution. Joint meetings with stakeholders and policy makers to share risk pathways and opportunities for co-benefits in the prioritization and funding of interventions to address water quality and quantity and protect Planetary Health.

4.2. Air Pollution and Urban Health

GoGreen Next and **PLANET4HEALTH** both focus on air pollution, with GoGreen Next addressing urban air pollution in the EU and PLANET4HEALTH studying air pollution in South Africa.

Collaboration Opportunity: Exchange of data and tools for air quality monitoring, particularly in urban settings. Projects could collaborate on developing **standardized indicators** for air pollution and its health impacts.

4.3. Mental Health and Well-being

GoGreen Next, **PLANET4HEALTH**, and **MOSAIC** all address mental health and well-being in the context of environmental degradation. GoGreen Next focuses on perceptions of climate change including climate anxiety, PLANET4HEALTH on mental well-being in South Africa and Spain, and MOSAIC on health and well-being in Maasai communities, SPRINGS on attitudes and perceptions of how climate change impacts water quality and quantity, TULIP will investigate attitudes and values towards loss of ecosystems and their services due to plastic pollution.

Collaboration Opportunity: Develop a **shared framework** for assessing mental health impacts across different environmental contexts. Projects could also collaborate on **policy recommendations** for addressing mental health in vulnerable populations.

4.4. Vector-Borne Diseases

PLANET4HEALTH and **MOSAIC** both study sand fly and mosquito-borne diseases, with PLANET4HEALTH in the Iberian Peninsula and MOSAIC in the Amazon region.

Collaboration Opportunity: Share data on vector distribution, climate suitability, and disease transmission models. Projects could also collaborate on developing **early warning systems** for vector-borne diseases.

4.5. Open Science and Data Sharing

MOSAIC and **TULIP** are both committed to open science, with constraints related to human data accessibility that all the projects are facing (please see below).

Collaboration Opportunity: Establish a **Cluster-wide data sharing agreement** that respects the restrictions of each project while promoting open access to non-sensitive data. Projects could also collaborate on developing **open tools** for data analysis and dissemination.

4.6. Nature-Based Solutions

TULIP and **SPRINGS** both explore nature-based solutions, such as constructed wetlands for water treatment and reforestation, and **GoGreen Next** employs urban parks to mitigate noise and air pollution.

Collaboration Opportunity: Joint research on the effectiveness of nature-based solutions in different environmental contexts. Projects could also collaborate on **policy papers** advocating for nature-based interventions.

5. Mitigating Restrictions and Overcoming Challenges

While there are clear opportunities for collaboration, there are also **restrictions and differing views** among the projects that need to be addressed to facilitate effective collaboration:

5.1. Data Restrictions

Challenge: All projects have restrictions on sharing human health data due to General Data Protection Regulation and associated ethics.

Solution: Establish a **data anonymization protocol** that allows for the sharing of aggregated data without compromising individual privacy. Projects could also explore **synthetic data generation** for modeling purposes. The project will jointly address issues of **data harmonization and standardization**, where needed.

5.2. Differing Methodologies

Challenge: Projects employ different methodologies, which can make it difficult to compare results or integrate data.

Solution: Develop **standardized protocols** for data collection and analysis, particularly in areas of overlap (e.g., water quality, air pollution). Projects could also organize **methodology workshops** to share best practices.

5.3. Policy Translation

Challenge: Projects have different approaches to policy translation, with some focusing on health technology assessments (HTA) and others on participatory approaches.

Solution: utilize the **Policy Working Group** within the Cluster (WG1) to harmonize policy translation efforts. This group could develop a **shared policy framework** that incorporates the strengths of each project's approach. Finally, the group can seek ways to maximize joint **stakeholder access**.

6. Future Collaborations

WORKING GROUPS

To further enhance synergies and avoid overlaps, the Planetary Health Cluster will establish one new working group:

WG4: Interventions (nature-based and other solutions)

which will be co-coordinated by projects TULIP, SPRINGS, and PLANET4HEALTH.

The Cluster will furthermore introduce one new working sub-group on:

Indicators for monitoring and evaluation

as part of the WG2. This subgroup will be coordinated by project TULIP.

Proposed new Working group and Working sub-group:

1. WG2 sub-group: Planetary Health Indicators for monitoring and evaluation

The Cluster is committed to developing and piloting indicators that can be used to monitor selected processes and issues. In the inception phase, the projects agreed to collect the independent indicator-production efforts in each project using a short survey. In the cluster activities, the projects will collaborate to establish a conceptual framework reflecting the Planetary Health perspective, pathways and outcomes to health from source and highlight potential quantifiable variables (indicators). The Cluster will establish a sub-workgroup that will lead the indicator-related efforts. The indicators will be introduced in the DMP Version 2.

2. WG4: Planetary Health Interventions (nature-based and other multi-sectoral solutions)

The Cluster is committed to identifying interventions that address the impact of climate change on environmental degradation. Planetary health interventions can have **significant co-benefits** supporting effective mitigation and adaptation at local, regional, and global scales. The working group will establish a conceptual framework for identification, prioritization, and assessing interventions that cross major planetary boundaries. The working group will interact closely with the existing Translation to policy working group, to ensure that co-benefits of planetary health interventions can be assessed and prioritized by policy makers to ensure their successful uptake.

THEMATIC WORKSHOPS

The Cluster will organize four thematic workshops (TWs) during its lifetime:

- TW1: Conceptualization of planetary health, interdisciplinarity and open science. Organized at month 18 of the Cluster, by WGs 1, 2, and 3.
- TW2 : Data science and indicators. Organized at month 24 of the Cluster, by WG 2 and WG 4.
- TW3: Equitable outcomes, vulnerability assessments, and resilience. Organized at month 36 of the Cluster, by all WGs.
- TW4: Building interventions for cross-sectoral impacts, action and policy supporting adaptation and mitigation strategies for planetary health. Organized at month 48 of the

7. Strategy for inclusion and increased participation

To enhance participation and engagement in the Planetary Health cluster and each of the working groups, we have developed the following strategies. First, each working group requires attendance and active involvement from at least two non-coordinators per working group, fostering shared responsibility and broader collaboration. Second, the cluster working groups actively seek participation from both North and South researchers, ensuring that voices from diverse geographical and institutional backgrounds contribute to discussions and decision-making. Third, the working groups actively encourage the participation of junior and mid-level scientists, providing them with opportunities for leadership, mentorship, and meaningful engagement. Finally, there is a focused communication strategy to raise awareness of and participation in the cluster within each project. One-page overviews, summarizing key activities and opportunities of the cluster will be shared within each project's internal channels. Each project will actively encourage in-person participation at the annual Planetary Health Cluster meetings. The annual meetings will further strengthen relationships across the cluster through presentations by junior researchers, thematic breakout sessions, speed-dating and networking events. This will further reinforce engagement and allow members to connect, share ideas, and strengthen collaboration across the working groups.

8. Conclusion

The Planetary Health Cluster represents a collaborative effort to address the complex interplay between environmental degradation and health impacts. By harmonizing approaches, promoting synergies, and strengthening the Science4Policy link, the Cluster aims to contribute to evidence-based decision-making and build capacity for environment and health research. This document serves as the backbone for the Cluster's scientific strategy, providing a framework for the projects to align their efforts and maximize their impact.

Annex 1

Draft Agenda of the first thematic workshop

Date, time, place: June 4, 2025, 1-6 PM, Brussels

Organizers: WGs 1, 2, and 3

Format: Hybrid

Agreed approaches: World café discussion type, leading to the joint statement as an output, open only to the Cluster partners as participants, moderated by a minimum 4 early-career researchers, hybrid meeting with online participation possible

Session 1 (1.5 hours)

opening presentations – 15 minutes, discussions - 1 hour, wrap-up - 15 minutes

Themes:

One Health and Planetary Health –similarities and differences, working definition.

Methodological approaches to problems of planetary health.

Sustainable science.

Break (30 minutes)

Session 2 (1.5 hours)

opening presentations – 15 minutes, discussions - 1 hour, wrap-up - 15 minutes

Themes:

Co-production of knowledge and participatory approaches.

Open science in a broad sense (as, for example, defined by UNESCO principles).

Interdisciplinarity, multidisciplinary, and transdisciplinarity.

Break (15 minutes)

Plenary (45 minutes)

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